

Determination of Aluminium in Iron Ores

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Investigation was undertaken to provide a widely applicable analytical method for the routine determination of aluminium content of iron ore. Published methods tend to be tedious, time consuming and inaccurate. A procedure, which overcomes these difficulties to a large extent, based on preliminary separation of iron by the ion exchange method (Dowex-1) and colorimetric determination of Al by 8-hydroxy quinoline in CHCl_3 at pH 8.5-9.5 is described.

A LUMINIUM is a common constituent of iron ore and is usually present in small amounts. The determination of aluminium in iron ores is important for the evaluation of the ores for metallurgical purposes. Although many methods have been recommended for estimating Al in iron ores, they are not reliable. The difficulties are the separation of aluminium from the major element Fe, and the adoption of a suitable method for the estimation of Al. The classical methods for determination of Al in iron ores are tedious and inaccurate. Lang and Reifer determined Al in presence of Fe by using tartrate and KCN^1 . Lundell² and Kassner and Ozier³ determined Al gravimetrically as aluminium oxinate in the presence of Ti, V, etc. But this procedure must be carefully performed to obtain accurate values. Weberly and Bassett⁴ adopted mercury cathode electrolysis to separate Fe. The method is cumbersome in manipulation and time consuming. Moreover, a method that needs a lengthy separation of Fe and Ti is not reliable and exact in selection of a procedure. The systematic study on the colorimetric determination of Al as aluminium oxinate made by Gentry and Sherrington⁵ revealed the role of pH and interferences of other elements. To apply colorimetric method, a preliminary separation of Al from iron^{6,7} is necessary. Attempts made in various laboratories to apply the separation led to erratic results. Kassner and Ozier adopted an extractive colorimetric method in the presence of iron by using an ammonical solution containing tartrate and KCN.

The present communication describes a convenient and accurate method for routine determination of aluminium in iron ores by the combined ion exchange solvent extraction separation of Al as aluminium oxinate at pH 8.5-9.5 in CHCl_3 and the measurement of its absorbance at 390 nm.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions : All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. 1 Stock solution of aluminium (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) was prepared by dissolving

potassium alum, $\text{KAl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 0.25 M HCl. 1% solution of 8-hydroxy quinoline (BDH) in CHCl_3 (E. Merck) was used as the complexing agent.

Equipment : Spectronic-20, Bausch and Lomb spectrophotometer was used for the measurements of absorbance at 390 nm using a glass cell of 1 cm path length.

Anion exchange technique : Dowex 1-X8 resin (200 mesh) in the chloride form was used as a strong base anion exchanger. A slurry of the resin in water was poured into a 25 ml burette fitted with a glass wool plug at the bottom. The column had an internal diameter 1 cm and a length of 10 cm. The effluent flow rate was 1 ml per min.

Procedure : 2.5 g sample of the finely ground iron ore was weighed in a 250 ml beaker, treated with 30-35 ml conc. HCl (sp. gr. 1.18) and heated slowly on a hot plate until the ore dissolved. The glass cover was rinsed, the solution evaporated to dryness and the residue baked for 1 hr. The baked residue was treated with 100 ml dilute HCl (1 : 1) and warmed to a clear solution and filtered. The filtrate was preserved. The residue was ignited in platinum crucible, cooled and weighed. It was treated with HF to volatilize silica, ignited, cooled and weighed again to determine silica content. The silica free residue was fused with 2 g Na_2CO_3 and extracted with 5% HCl solution. The extracts were added to the preserved filtrate and the volume made up to 500 ml. 20 ml aliquot, equivalent to 0.1 g sample, was evaporated to dryness in 50 ml beaker, dissolved in 5 ml 9 M HCl and passed through the column at the rate of 1 ml/min and collected in a 100 ml volumetric flask. The resin was then washed with 50 ml of 9M HCl in 4 instalments and the eluates collected in the same flask. The Al solution was made up to 100 ml volume and used for analysis.

10 ml water, 0.2 g tartaric acid and 1 ml 3% H_2O_2 were added to 10 ml aliquot of the Al solution in a separatory funnel and shaken. Then 10 ml NH_4OH was added. The pH was adjusted to

8.9-9.5, 10 ml of 1% oxine solution was added, the whole was shaken for 2 min and allowed to stand for 10 min. The CHCl_3 layer was taken in 25 ml vol flask. The aqueous layer was extracted with another 10 ml CHCl_3 and finally 5 ml CHCl_3 . The combined CHCl_3 extracts were diluted to 25 ml with CHCl_3 and the absorbance was measured at 390 nm. Al content was determined from calibration curve prepared by measurements with known amounts of Al. A blank was run in which 10 ml of water was used in place of the 10 ml Al solution. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF ALUMINIUM

Iron Ore Samples	Fe%	Al% (by conventional classical method)*	Al% (by the present method)
S ₁	68.67	1.95	1.90
S ₂	68.94	1.80	1.88
S ₃	65.90	1.45	1.51
S ₄	68.68	0.40	0.50

*Fe separation by Dynacath Hg-electrolysis, Ti separation by NaOH and Al determination in the filtrate as Al-oxinate at pH 5-6.

The above combined procedure was repeated with synthetic Al solution containing Fe and Ti. The results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF ALUMINIUM IN A SYNTHETIC MIXTURE

Fe (taken) mg	Ti (taken) mg	Al (taken) μg	Al (found) μg	% error
56	2	400	380	-5%
56	2	800	780	-3%

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that the results obtained by the two procedures were quite satisfactory. Table 2 shows the recovery of Al in a synthetic mixture, prepared from known quantities of Fe, Ti and Al. The concentration of Fe and Ti normally found in iron ores had no apparent effect on Al recovery

from ion exchange separation and could therefore be disregarded as a source of interference. The amount of Al found (Table 2) was slightly less than the amount added. This method has the following advantages.

- Iron forms anionic chloro complex in 9 M HCl and is retained strongly on the anion exchanger. Al^{3+} and Ti^{4+} pass out through the column and are collected as eluates^{7,8,9}. The interference of titanium in subsequent colorimetric determination of aluminium as oxinate complex in CHCl_3 is removed by adding H_2O_2 so as to form peroxy titanate acid retained in the aqueous phase.
- The time required to effect separation of iron by ion exchange and subsequent spectrophotometric determination of Al is far less than the conventional classical method.
- The method is selective and sensitive.
- Quite a large number of samples can be analysed for Al by setting up several ion exchange columns and using 100 ml volumetric flasks and separating funnels. The conventional classical method requires costly apparatus and much longer time to effect similar Fe and Ti separations.

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